

Educational Resources

Examples of citizen science school-based approaches

Title

Cos4Cloud Citizen Science & Environmental Education for Sustainability Educational Scenario Guide

About this educational resource

This **Cos4Cloud Educational Scenario Guide** was developed to support the creation of **Educational Scenarios** that are part of citizen science-based environmental education activities and interventions. Educational Scenarios are part of Cos4Cloud's work on [education](#) led by Cos4Cloud project partner National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA) Environmental Education Lab. The [Cos4Cloud](#) project has developed thirteen technological services to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations. Cos4Cloud includes nine [Citizen Observatories \(COs\)](#). NKUA has [designed and demonstrated educational content](#) which can be adapted to support learning at primary, secondary or university level in Environmental Education (EE) and Educational Sustainable Development (ESD). This content showcases examples of citizen science school-based approaches that include examples demonstrating citizen observatories involved in Cos4Cloud and the project services.

This Guide was adapted from a template* initially used as a resource for Greek Environmental Education teachers and school educational stakeholders as part of the co-design of educational scenarios in the context of the Cos4Cloud project. These supporting resources and outputs were originally developed and delivered by NKUA in Greek and this Guide has been adapted in English as part of the [Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub](#).

*This guide has been adapted from the NKUA Citizen Science & Environmental Education for Sustainability Educational Scenario Template. (translated from Greek into English).

Cos4Cloud Education Lead Partner

Description

This Guide is provided as a step-by-step guidance tool to support those interested in devising and implementing Citizen Science & Environmental Education for Sustainability educational scenarios and activities for use in schools and other educational settings using frameworks developed by NKUA.

There are two parts with guidance on the fields to complete, inviting you to think about how to share all the necessary information i.e. your rationale, technical details, and the implementation of a proposed educational activity in a comprehensive and codified way. This helps to make it easy and transparent to understand, use, re-use or modify. This Guide was adapted from a Template which is a useful, practical and reflective tool for every teacher, educational practitioner, homeschool learner, or for anyone who would like to get involved with the practice of citizen science in schools or other educational settings.

In the **first section**, there is guidance about how to present the “identity” of the scenario: your main idea, what this involves, the “target group,” the key topic or issue to be addressed, the duration, the **Cos4Cloud citizen observatories** and / or tools to be used, connections with a school curriculum, etc., and the expected learning outcomes in terms of a range of literacies and competencies.

In the **second section**, there is information to help provide a detailed description of your educational scenario or activity, stage by stage, with information on: the themes, goals, steps, time and context, and the activities and resources involved, etc.

Key points to consider, within an educational scenario or activity development and evaluation process:

- The scenario identity (title, team members, keywords, core theme, central environmental/ sustainability issue addressed, grade / class / age group, total duration / number of stages, summary),
- The link between citizen science and Environmental Education (EE) / Education for Sustainable Development (ESD),
- Pedagogical use of the citizen science digital platforms i.e. citizen observatory and tools, for example iSpot, Pl@ntNet and Natusfera,
- Pedagogical innovation and added value,
- Strengths and weaknesses of the ideas and the scenario’s deployment,
- Activities that can be adjusted and used in other contexts (i.e. online as in the Covid-19 period),
- Overall appraisal of the scenario.

Cos4Cloud Coordinator

CITIZEN SCIENCE & ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABILITY

Educational Scenario & Activities Template Guide

Title “Insert a title of your educational scenario or activity”

Writing (Authors/ Educational Designers) team “Fill in the details of the members of the team designing this educational scenario (name, identity, title)”

THE EDUCATIONAL SCENARIO

SECTION 1:

What is the main idea of the scenario?

Please indicate the central idea-theme that runs throughout the educational scenario
(Up to 50 words)

Brief description

Briefly describe the educational scenario as a whole; what is the rationale and how it will be deployed.
(Up to 350 words)

Which learning group is it aimed at?

Please indicate the age, school grade / level to which the educational scenario is addressed.

If you consider that it addresses more than one age group / school grade, please specify.

Include, whether it is specifically addressed to a group with disabilities / special learning difficulties or whether it includes those with specific learning difficulties.

Main issue / theme around which the scenario is developed

Please refer to the environmental and / or sustainability issues it addresses. What is the 'local' case of the main issue(s) addressed by the educational scenario?
(Up to 250 words)

Other issues / topics addressed

List any other issues (they may be unrelated to the main one) or topics the educational scenario also deals with.
(Up to 150 words)

Duration of implementation

Please indicate (a) the number of months within the school year and (b) the total number of teaching hours required for the implementation period.

Which Cos4Cloud platforms (citizen observatories, services, or tools) are you using?

Please indicate which of the Cos4Cloud platforms, services or tools are being integrated in the educational scenario (there may be more than one).

Related connections with the school curriculum

Indicate which subjects in the school curriculum are linked to the educational scenario (e.g., history, biology, literature, civic society, language, computer science, etc.)

Learning Objectives / expected learning outcomes - to be achieved at different literacy levels

Select and clearly justify whether and how this scenario meets the learning objectives of any of the following literacy levels:

Learning Objectives / expected learning outcomes (continued)

Environmental Literacy (development of specialised knowledge, skills, attitudes, and experience in relation to the environment and various environmental issues/matters)

Scientific Literacy (development of specialised knowledge, skills, attitudes, and experience in relation to scientific concepts, subjects, and research processes; and knowledge production in the natural, social, or human sciences, or in the humanities (please indicate which ones))

Citizenship Literacy (development of specialised knowledge, skills, attitudes, and experience in how to exercise one's rights and duties as citizen, expressed in terms of active interest in and responsibility for the public, an active interest and concern for the common welfare of all, participation, and active engagement for the common welfare of all at local, European, and national level, etc. (please indicate which ones))

Digital Literacy (development of specialised knowledge, skills, attitudes, and experience in relation to the use of specific digital technologies and tools (please specify which ones))

Basic literacy (development of knowledge and skills in relation to basic knowledge and skills in language, mathematics, foreign languages, arts (please indicate which ones))

Learning Objectives / expected learning outcomes pursued in terms of a range of different competencies

Select and justify precisely whether and how any learning outcomes are achieved in the context of the educational scenario for any of the following key competences?

- Creative thinking
- Critical thinking
- Problem solving

Learning Objectives / expected learning outcomes pursued in terms of a range of different competencies (continued)

- Decision making
- Learning to learn
- Data analysis and information analysis
- Communication of ideas and information
- Flexibility and adaptability
- Collaboration - working in teams
- Leadership and responsibility
- Development of initiatives
- Project delivery and consistency in implementation
- Sense of personal and social responsibility

SECTION 2:

Detailed description of the scenario in successive stages

Describe the development of the educational scenario in stages (not less than 2 - no more than 5), briefly listing the activities you plan to implement in each stage; and specifying the time frame and the spatial context of implementation of each of them.

Stage 1

Title: (give a title indicating how you are defining this stage in relation to the others)

Brief description: (briefly describe the whole stage and explain what its teaching purpose is (up to 150 words))

Duration: (in teaching hours)

Spatial context: (where it takes place – it may take place in several spaces, i.e. in the classroom, in the hallway, in the courtyard, in the school grounds, in the neighbourhood, in the park, in the streets of the town, in a museum, in a home, etc.)

Stage 1 (continued)

Activities (see note below*):

- 1. Title:** followed by a brief description of the activity and a reference to the aim it serves (Up to 50 words)
- 2. Title:** followed by a brief description of the activity and a reference to the aim it serves (Up to 50 words)
- 3. Other activities**

*You may list as many activities as you consider necessary and appropriate to include in this stage. Indicate separately, in such a way as to be readily distinguishable, those activities which are based on, familiarise and /or pedagogically engage learners with the CO platform or tool.

Stage 2

Title: (give a title indicating how you are defining this stage in relation to the others)

Brief description: (briefly describe the whole stage and explain what its teaching purpose is) (up to 150 words)

Duration: (in teaching hours)

Spatial context: (where it takes place – it may take place in several spaces, such as in the classroom, in the hallway, in the courtyard, in the school grounds, in the neighbourhood, in the park, in the streets of the town, in a museum, in a home, etc.)

Activities (see note below*):

- 1. Title:** followed by a brief description of the activity and a reference to the aim it serves (Up to 50 words)
- 2. Title:** followed by a brief description of the activity and a reference to the aim it serves (Up to 50 words)
- 3. Other activities**

*List as many activities you consider necessary and appropriate to include in this stage. Mark them separately, in a way that can be readily distinguishable, i.e. activities which are based on, can familiarise with and / or pedagogically engage learners.

Stage 3

Do the same as above for each of the other stages.

Other groups involved

Indicate any other groups (e.g., teaching staff, experts, professionals, NGOs, the local community, etc.) involved in the different stages of the implementation of the scenario. And indicate how you will evoke and support their involvement. (Up to 150 words)

Evaluation of the implementation of the educational scenario

Describe the ways in which you plan to evaluate the educational scenario, during or after the implementation.

Evaluation activities*:

- 1. Title:** followed by a brief description of the activity and a reference to the goal that it serves (Up to 50 words)
- 2. Title:** followed by a brief description of the activity and a reference to the goal that it serves (Up to 50 words)
- 3. Other activities**

*List as many evaluation activities you consider appropriate, necessary, and suitable to include in this stage. Mark them separately, in a way that is readily distinguishable, stating the evaluation activities associated with the engagement with a citizen observatory platform, service or tool.

Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#)

This guide is an educational resource that supports the development of Educational Scenarios based on a Template that is part of the citizen science and environmental education content and activities for schools developed by NKUA in the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). **NKUA team authors:** Maria Daskolia, Naya Grillia and Dimitris Gkatzos. **Title: Cos4Cloud Citizen Science & Environmental Education for Sustainability Educational Scenario Guide.** This Guide is part of the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

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